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INTRUSION DETECTION USING MACHINE LEARNING ON KDD-CUP-99 DATASET: ANALYSIS OF FEATURE SELECTION

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Abstract. This article discusses methods for selecting features to build models of intrusion detection systems and how to improve the effectiveness of detection with them. The correct classification of the features is also mentioned.

Keywords: intrusion detection, attack, feature, feature selection, DoS, Probe, R2L, U2R.

1. Introduction

When intrusion detection systems are built together with artificial intelligence systems, one of the most important processes is to correctly extract features from network packets and use the most necessary ones. This process is called feature selection [1].

Feature selection is the process of isolating the most consistent, non-redundant, and relevant features to use in model construction. Methodically reducing the size of datasets is important as the size and variety of datasets continue to grow. The main goal of feature selection is to improve the performance of a predictive model and reduce the computational cost of modeling [3].

Why Feature Selection is Important

Feature selection is an invaluable asset for data scientists. Understanding how to select important features in machine learning is crucial to the efficacy of the machine learning algorithm. Irrelevant, redundant, and noisy features can pollute an algorithm, negatively impacting learning performance, accuracy, and computational cost. Feature selection is increasingly important as the size and complexity of the average dataset continues to grow exponentially [2].

2. Feature selection methods

Feature selection algorithms are categorized as either supervised, which can be used for labeled data; or unsupervised, which can be used for unlabeled data. Unsupervised techniques are classified as filter methods, wrapper methods, embedded

methods, or hybrid methods:

Filter methods: Filter methods select features based on statistics rather than feature selection cross-validation performance. A selected metric is applied to identify irrelevant attributes and perform recursive feature selection. Filter methods are either univariate, in which an ordered ranking list of features is established to inform the final selection of feature subset; or multivariate, which evaluates the relevance of the features as a whole, identifying redundant and irrelevant features.

Wrapper methods: Wrapper feature selection methods consider the selection of a set of features as a search problem, whereby their quality is assessed with the preparation, evaluation, and comparison of a combination of features to other combinations of features. This method facilitates the detection of possible interactions amongst variables. Wrapper methods focus on feature subsets that will help improve the quality of the results of the clustering algorithm used for the selection. Popular examples include Boruta feature selection and Forward feature selection.

Embedded methods: Embedded feature selection methods integrate the feature selection machine learning algorithm as part of the learning algorithm, in which classification and feature selection are performed simultaneously. The features that will contribute the most to each iteration of the model training process are carefully extracted. Random forest feature selection, decision tree feature selection, and LASSO feature selection are common embedded methods.

How to Choose a Feature Selection Method

Choosing the best feature selection method depends on the input and output in consideration:

- Numerical Input, Numerical Output;
- Numerical Input, Categorical Output;
- Categorical Input, Numerical Output;
- Categorical Input, Categorical Output [4].

3. Proposed method

All features are made numerical using one-Hot-encoding. The features are scaled to avoid features with large values that may weigh too much in the results.

Eliminate redundant and irrelevant data by selecting a subset of relevant features that fully represents the given problem. Univariate feature selection with ANOVA F-test. This analyzes each feature individually to determine the strength of the relationship between the feature and labels. Using SecondPercentile method (sklearn.feature_selection to select features based on percentile of the highest scores. When this subset is found: Recursive Feature Elimination (RFE is applied. For proposed method used KDD_CUP_99 dataset.

KDD Cup 1999 Data

This is the data set used for The Third International Knowledge Discovery and Data Mining Tools Competition, which was held in conjunction with KDD-99 The Fifth International Conference on Knowledge Discovery and Data Mining. The competition task was to build a network intrusion detector, a predictive model capable of distinguishing between “bad” connections, called intrusions or attacks, and “good” normal connections. This database contains a standard set of data to be audited, which includes a wide variety of intrusions simulated in a military network environment [5].

Train dataset dimensioned for unify attack types to categories:

Dimensions of DoS: 488735

Dimensions of Probe: 101384

Dimensions of R2L: 98403

Dimensions of U2R: 97329

Feature Selection

1. Univariate Feature Selection using ANOVA F-test

DoS	Probe	R2L	U2R
logged_in, count, srv_count, srv_diff_host_rate, dst_host_count, dst_host_same_src_port_rate, dst_host_srv_diff_host_rate, Protocol_type_icmp, Protocol_type_tcp, Protocol_type_udp, service_ecr_i, service_http	count, rerror_rate, srv_rerror_rate, same_srv_rate, diff_srv_rate, dst_host_diff_srv_rate, dst_host_srv_diff_host_rate, dst_host_rerror_rate, dst_host_srv_rerror_rate, service_eco_i, flag_RSTR, flag_SF	src_bytes, hot, num_failed_logins, is_guest_login, dst_host_srv_count, dst_host_same_src_port_rate, dst_host_srv_diff_host_rate, service_ftp, service_ftp_data, service_http, service_imap4, flag_RSTO	urgent, hot, lroot_shell, lnum_file_creations, lnum_shells, error_rate, dst_host_srv_count, dst_host_same_src_port_rate, dst_host_srv_diff_host_rate, service_ftp_data, service_http, service_telnet

Table 2. Selected features Univariate Feature Selection using ANOVA F-test

2. Recursive Feature Elimination for feature

DoS	Probe	R2L	U2R
count, srv_count, Protocol_type_udp , dst_host_same_src _port_rate, logged_in, dst_host_count, srv_diff_host_rate, Protocol_type_tcp, service_ecr_i, dst_host_srv_diff_ host_rate, service_http, Protocol_type_icm p	dst_host_diff_srv _rate, dst_host_srv_diff _host_rate, flag_RSTR, same_srv_rate, service_eco_i, dst_host_rerror_ra te, flag_SF, count, dst_host_srv_rerr or_rate, diff_srv_rate, error_rate, srv_rerror_rate	src_bytes, hot, dst_host_same_src _port_rate, service_ftp_data, num_failed_logins, dst_host_srv_count , service_imap4, dst_host_srv_diff_ host_rate, is_guest_login, flag_RSTO, service_http, service_ftp	lroot_shell, dst_host_srv_count , lnum_file_creation s, hot, dst_host_same_src _port_rate, service_ftp_data, dst_host_srv_diff_ host_rate, service_telnet, service_http, error_rate, lnum_shells, urgent

Table 3. Getting importance from previous selected features

Recursive Feature Elimination, selecting 13 features from 119

Features selected for DoS:	src_bytes, dst_bytes, wrong_fragment, lnum_compromised, count, same_srv_rate, dst_host_same_srv_rate, dst_host_error_rate, dst_host_srv_error_rate, service_ecr_i, service_tim_i, flag_REJ, flag_RSTR
Features selected for Probe:	src_bytes, dst_bytes, error_rate, same_srv_rate, dst_host_count, dst_host_same_srv_rate, dst_host_diff_srv_rate, dst_host_srv_diff_host_rate, service_eco_i, service_ftp_data, flag_OTH, flag_RSTR, flag_SH
Features selected for R2L:	duration, src_bytes, hot, num_failed_logins, lnum_access_files, count, dst_host_srv_count, dst_host_diff_srv_rate, dst_host_same_src_port_rate, dst_host_srv_diff_host_rate, dst_host_srv_rerror_rate, service_ftp_data, service_imap4

Features selected for U2R:	duration, src_bytes, dst_bytes, lnum_compromised, lroot_shell, lnum_root, lnum_file_creations, dst_host_srv_count, dst_host_same_srv_rate, dst_host_srv_diff_host_rate, service_ftp_data, service_other, service_telnet
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Table 4. 13 most important selected features

4. Conclusion

Analyzing the above, it is important to choose the features used in initial training to build attack detection systems and make their models more efficient. Keeping the existing methods interdependent also increases efficiency, reduces time and resource consumption, and reduces false alarm rate. At the end selected most important 13 features to detect attacks for every category.

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